

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHER CHARACTERISTICS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF EARLY CHILDHOOD CARE EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN ZAMFARA STATE

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Abstract

This study focused on the relationship between teacher characteristics and implementation of early childhood care education in Zamfara State. The population of the study is one hundred and twelve (112) Early Childhood Care Education head teachers and two hundred and seventy teachers (270) teachers. The sample size of the study was 86 head teachers and 159 teachers selected from the 86 Early Childhood Centers. The sample size was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1971) table for determining sample size. The data was presented and analyzed using descriptive data analysis and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Simple percentage was used to present data on the three research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the three research hypotheses. Self-designed Teachers Characteristics Inventory (TCI) and Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Questionnaire (IECCEQ) were used for data collection and analysis after certifying its validity by experts and reliability through test re-test method. Some of the findings of the study showed that there was significant relationships between teacher qualification, specialization, experience and implementation of early child care education programme in Zamfara State. Major recommendations of the study were that government should improve the training and recruitment of qualified and specialized teachers while experienced teachers should be assign to ECCE classes in all the nursery schools to maintained effective programme implementation.

Introduction

It is widely believed that exposure to a wide variety of activities and of social and mental interactions with children and adults (teachers) greatly enhance a child's ability to learn (Erikson, 1963 & Jackson, 1966). Early Childhood Care Education Programme is such that provides preparatory educational experience to young children. Enough room is made for flexibility such that during school hours children move about and mix freely and work or play in small groups. The play and work of these children were to be carried out under the guidance of an experienced teacher.

The teacher, who is the real handler of teaching/learning facilities in the school, has to ensure their safe keeping. He has to operate the audio/visual teaching learning facilities put in place in his class. The teacher deals with the nursery pupils in their academic life, he teaches the pupils all the rudiments of reading, writing and arithmetic. He should be very friendly so that he/she is seen as a replica of the father/mother of pupils in the school (Olowosulu, 1997). The need to have qualified, experience and specialized teachers is seen to be highly desirable if the educational objectives for early child care as contained in the National Policy on Education (N.P.E, 2004) are to be achieved and adequately implemented.

The implementation of education programme can be meaningfully effective, then the need of teachers have to be acknowledged and provided for. Nkeje (1995) cited in Musa (2010) asserted that, one of the most crucial factor that has to be accepted is the fact that success or failure in the management and policy implementation of any educational programme, early childhood care education inclusive rest more squarely on the quality and commitments of teachers. Therefore, professionally trained, competent, committed and well-motivated teachers are central factors in effective goals achievement of educational programme's policies and national development.

Almy (1975) suggest that if early childhood education programme objectives are to be realized, we need to develop a new professional who knows how to locate and coordinate the resources needed to foster full human development. The main thrust of this study therefore, is to examine the relationship between teachers' qualification, teacher experience, teacher specialization and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education in Zamfara State.

Statement of the Problem

Many problems appear to be affecting the standard of education in terms of quality output. One can see clearly how unqualified and drop out are always been sent to man the affairs of teaching in the nursery classes, even though most of the early child care centers, shows to be well staffed but only a handful of them have required qualifications to teach, most of the teachers are either Grade II referred or secondary school leavers and drop outs.

Early Child Care Education which appears to be the bed rock or foundation level of all other types of education needs to be looked into, need to be known how this programme operate. Zamfara State Government introduced Early Childhood

Education by requesting that Early Childhood Education classes/section be opened in some public primary school to serve as model centers, while teacher training capacity and supply in the state has not kept pace with the rapid growth of nursery School. There is no single teacher training institution in the state previously which offer Early Childhood Education teacher training, until recently when Zamfara State College of Education Maru established a Department of Early Childhood Care and Education for the year 2010/2011 session. This problem of not having trained teachers may have largely affect the implementation of early childhood education policy in the state and the quality of education provided in these institutions. Worthy of note also is that most of the proprietors running nursery schools in the state are business people not educationists.

This study was therefore intended to examine the relationship between teacher qualification, teacher experience, teacher specialization and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme (ECCEP) in Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The research will address the following research questions:

1. Is there any relationship between teachers' qualification and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State?
2. Is there any relationship between teacher experience and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State?
3. Is there any relationship between teachers' specialization and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State?

Objectives of the Study

This research was guided by the following objectives:

1. Find out the relationship between teacher qualification and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State.
2. Find out the relationship between teacher experience and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State.
3. Find out the relationship between teacher specialization and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State.

Research Hypotheses

Three hypotheses that are inline with research question and objectives were formulated in order to guide the conduct of the research, thus:

1. There is no significance relationship between teacher qualification and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme in Zamfara State.
2. There is no significance relationship between teacher experience and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education programme in Zamfara State.
3. There is no significance relationship between teacher specialization and implementation of Early Childhood Care Education programme in Zamfara State.

Conceptual Frame Work

The period before the child reaches the age of attending Primary School is very critical in influencing his/her learning achievement in future (Shekari, 1979). To ensure that children at this level receive appropriate training and care, the National Policy on Education (2013) describes the Early Childhood Care Education as care, protection, stimulation and learning promoted in children from age 0-5 years in a crèche or nursery. The Federal Government of Nigeria introduced Early Childhood Care Education Programme as one of the main component of basic education as contained in the National Policy on Education (NPE). According to the NPE (2013), the purposes of pre-primary education include:

1. Smooth transition from the home to school
2. Preparing the child for the primary level
3. Provide adequate care and supervision for the child while their parents are at work.
4. Inculcating social norms, spirit of enquiry and teaching the child cooperation, team spirit and good health habits

Some of the recommendation laid in order to achieve the general purpose policy for Early Childhood Education stated that government shall promote the training of qualified Early Childhood Education school teachers in the schools (NPE, 2013).

The teacher according to Mbahi (2000) cited in Musa (2007) is a professional who transmits knowledge, direct and guide the learning processes; he (teacher) is expected to have appropriate knowledge and skills to pass on to his pupils. It is right to say that without good teacher preparation the whole policies and laws cannot be ascertain; National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) is explicit on teacher preparation for the education system, it stated clearly and unequivocal terms that, teacher education will continue to be given a major emphasis in all educational planning and development. Since the success of educational system as compiled by Daniel (2007) is reflected by the caliber of teachers in the system in terms of their characteristics such as qualification, experience and specialization and in this research its refers to the extent to which teachers were able to bring about the intended learning outcome that in turn lead to effective implementation of Early Childhood Care Education programme.

Theoretical Framework

The study was based on a Social System Theory. The social system theory was one of the behavioral approaches to educational administration postulated by Parson (1977). According to the author, a system is an organized collection of independent but interrelated elements or components set up to accomplish an overall goal. Social System Theory can be used clearly and concisely to understand the school structure, process as well as outcome and their interactions within a school system. Simply put, the school as a system has various input that are processed to produce output with feedback as represented in figure 1 below.

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Figure 1: The Social System Model

Source: Adapted from Parson (1977).

A school system consists of input, process and output. School input includes resources such as human resources and materials. This means schools recruit teachers, admit pupils and secure all facilities from community and the Ministry of Education. Input is processed by the school head through transforming available resources to create new products in terms of quality learning and effective use of teachers experience and specialization in order to train pupils for further transition into primary schools, which is the output of the school. The school uses public opinions to get feedback on the quality of products whether the opinions are constructive or not in order to ensure adequate implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme

Review of Empirical Studies

Various researchers and educators has stressed the effect of teachers influence on teaching and learning processes, one of such researchers that was reviewed is Sani (2004),who conducted a research on Teacher characteristics and operational efficiency: A case study of Kebbi State, the study aimed at examining the nature of operational difficulties encountered by teachers and the extent to which the characteristics of the teachers inhibit their efficiency within and outside the classrooms. It also examined the consequences of teacher inefficiency and proffer possible remedies. In conducting his Study a simple survey was conducted in Kebbi State. 150 teachers were randomly selected from 30 Secondary schools deliberately selected. 0.86 correlations coefficient was obtained through a structured test using Pearson's product moment. Responses were tallied and frequencies were converted to simple percentages.

The study found that poor teacher qualification affects the efficiency of the teacher to perform well in the classroom. The untrained teachers are generally unable to apply the right methods, techniques of teaching. These findings were in line with the present research which found that majority of the teachers in early childhood care education centers in Zamfara State do not have teaching qualification, teachers with less than one or two years' experience were found in most of the centers and the few teachers that are found with teaching qualification are not specialist in the area of early childhood education and thus cannot bring about the effective implementation of early childhood education. Both studies investigated on teacher characteristic.

What makes the current study unique is that it focused on Early Childhood Education programme in Zamfara State and on teacher qualification, experience and specialization as the determinant of the effectiveness of programme implementation of ECCEP.

Research Methodology

This study was conducted using descriptive survey design. The target population covered by this study was the entire 112 head teachers and 270 teachers across the three senatorial zones of Zamfara State. 86 Early Childhood Care Centers Were Selected and sampled for the study involving 86 head-teachers and 159 teachers making a total of 245 respondents. The selection of the sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1971) table for determining sample size.

In order to cover the areas of the investigation, understand the dimension of research problem and find out the data needed for the study two self-constructed instruments tagged Teachers Characteristics Inventory (TCI) and Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Questionnaire (IECCEQ) were used after certifying its validity by the expert from the Department of Educational Foundations, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. And the reliability of the instrument was also ascertained through a pilot study which was carried out in five school that were not among the selected schools for the study and the result of the pilot test indicated reliability index of 0.73 at 0.5 level of significant, which was adequate to say that the instruments were consistent and reliable.

Table 1: Populations and Sampling

	Population	Sample
Nursery schools	112	86
Head teachers	112	86
Teachers	270	159

Source: Field work 2012

Table 1 above shows a total population of 112 nursery schools and 270 teachers. The table also shows a total of 86 head teachers and 159 teachers as sample.

Descriptive Data Presentation

The following descriptive data was presented and analyzed to give picture of the teacher qualification, experience and specialization. The 3 hypotheses were also tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (*PPMCC*).

Table 2: Teacher Qualification

S/N	Qualification	Frequency	%
1	PhD in Education	0	0
2	MEd	2	1
3	B.Ed	28	11
4	NCE	42	17
5	TC II	31	13
6	None-teaching qualifications	142	58
	Total	245	100

Table 2 shows that the highest qualification of the teachers in the schools surveyed was M.Ed. Two of the teachers had M.Ed., 28 representing 11% had B.Ed., 42 teachers representing 17% had NCE, 31 teachers representing 13% had TC-II certificate while majority of them (142) representing 58% had non-teaching qualifications.

Table 3: Teacher Specialization

S/N	Specialization	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	ECCD	2	1
2	Primary Education	40	16
3	Specialization with education	73	30
4	Specialization without education	130	53
Total		245	100

Table 3 above shows that very few teachers (2) representing only 1% specialized in ECCD, 40 teachers representing 16% specialized in Primary Education, 73 teachers representing 30% specialized with education while 130 teachers representing 53% specialized without education.

Table 4: Teacher Experience

S/N	Experience	Frequency	%
1	Above 10 years	18	7
2	5-10 years	56	23
3	1-4 years	98	40
4	Less than 1 year	73	30
Total		245	100

Table 4 above shows that 18 teachers representing 7% had working experience of 10 years and above, 56 teachers representing 23% had working experience of 5-10 years, 98 teachers representing 40% had working experience of 1-4 years while 73 teachers representing 30% had less than 1 year working experience.

Table 5 Implementation of ECCD

S/No	Item Statement	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1.	The Objectives of ECCD clearly understood by the teachers and school heads.	75	30	170	70
2.	Teachers have and use a well stipulated syllabus in schools	100	41	145	59
3.	The content of ECCD perceived as is suitable for its implementation	200	82	45	18

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4.	Appropriate methods of teaching used in ECCD schools	141	58	104	53
5.	ECCD instructional materials used in schools.	133	54	112	45
6.	Schools' environments conducive for the implementation ECCD	102	38	152	63
7.	Teachers in schools handle ECCD classes professionally	103	42	142	58
8.	ECCD programme handled by competent and specialized teachers	77	32	168	68
9.	ECCD programme handled by experienced teachers	102	42	143	59
	Total	1033	46	1181	493
	Average	114	46	131	54

On the implementation of ECCD programme in the area of the study, Table 5 presents summary of teachers' responses on how they understood and manage ECCD in their respective schools. The data shows that 69% of respondents disagree with the view that objective of ECCD were clearly understood by teachers and school head while only 30% of the respondent agreed that objectives of ECCD were understood by teachers. Majority 59% respondent disagree that teacher have and used a well stipulated syllabus in schools. On the item description that the content of ECCD perceived as suitable for its implementation 82% agreed. Majority (58%) disagree with the view that appropriate method for teaching is used in ECCD schools. Majority 54% agreed that ECCD instructional materials used in schools. On the item description that school environment conducive for the implementation of ECCD 62% disagree with the view. Majority (58%) disagree that teachers in schools handle ECCD classes professionally. Majority (69%) disagree that ECCD programme handled by competent and specialized teachers. On the item description that ECCD programme handle by experience teachers 58% disagreed with the view. In summary 46% of respondent agree that ECCD were well implemented and majority of participants (54%) disagree that ECCD programme were well implemented in Zamfara state.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between teacher's qualification and implementation of early child care programme in Zamfara State.

Table 6: Relationship between Teacher Qualification (TQ) and Implementation of Early Child Care Education Programme (IECCDP).

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-value	Decision
TQ	245	32.28	4.55	488	0.199	0.195	H ₀₁ rejected
IECCP	245	29.75	5.77				

TQ =Teacher Qualification
IECCD =Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education

The table 5 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.199 was greater than the p-value of 0.195 at 488 degree of freedom using 0.05 level of significant. The hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between Teachers'

Qualification (TQ) and implementation of Early Child care programme (IECCP) in Zamfara State was rejected. This means that there was relationship between Teacher Qualification and Implementation of Early Child Care Programme in Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between teachers' specialization and implementation of early child care programme in Zamfara State.

Table 7: Relationship between Teachers' Specialization (TS) and Implementation of Early Child Care Education Programme (IECCP).

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-value	Decision
TS	245	34.48	4.78	488	0.201	0.195	H ₀₂ rejected
IECCP	245	29.75	5.67				

TS =Teacher Specialization
IECCD =Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education

Table 7, shows that the calculated r-value of 0.201 was greater than p-value of 0.195 at 488 degree of freedom using 0.05 level of significance. There is therefore strong relationship between teachers' specialization and implementation of early child care education programme in Zamfara State and therefore the hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between teachers experience and implementation of early childhood care programme in Zamfara State.

Table 8: Relationship between Teachers Experiences (TE) and Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme (IECCP).

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-value	Decision
TE	245	32.63	4.82	488	0.228	0.195	Ho ₃ rejected
IECCP	245	29.75	5.87				
TE	=Teacher Experience						
IECCD	=Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education						

Table 8 Shows that, the calculated r-value of 0.228 was less than the critical p-value of 0.195 at 488 degree of freedom using 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis which states that there is no significant relation between Teachers Experience (TE) and Implementation of Early Childcare Programme (IECCP) in Zamfara state was rejected. This means that there was significant relationship between teacher experience (TE) and Implementation of Early Child Care Education Programme (IECCP).

Summary of Major Findings

The major findings of the study are presented below:

1. There was significant relationship between teacher's qualification and Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme (IECCP) Zamfara State.
2. There was significant relationship between teacher's Specialization and Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme (IECCP) in Zamfara State
3. There was significant relationship between Teacher's Experience and Implementation of Early Childhood Care Education Programme (IECCP) in Zamfara State

Discussion of Findings

Based on the result of the findings of the study that 145 teachers representing 58% had non-teaching qualification and that shows that the implementation of ECCE

was ineffective and inefficient in majority of the centers, This shows that most of the schools lacked enough qualified teachers for ECCE and therefore affects the successful implementation of the programme in the area of the study. The hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between teacher qualification and the implementation of ECCE in the area of the study was therefore rejected.

On the relationship between teachers specialization and the implementation of ECCE, the results of the study shows that only 1% of teachers specialized in the area of ECCE in majority of the centers. This shows that most of the centers did not have specialized teachers for ECCE and therefore affects successful implementation of the programme in the area of the study. The hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between teacher specialization and the implementation of ECCE in the area of the study was therefore rejected.

On the relationship between teacher experience and the implementation of ECCE, the results of the study discovers that 40% of the teachers had working experience of 1-4 years, 30% had less than one year working experience and only 7% had experience that is above 10 years. The hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between teacher experience and implementation of ECCE in Zamfara State was rejected.

Conclusion

In line with the findings summarized above, the study concludes that there existed a significant relationships between teacher qualification, specialization, experience and the implementation of Early Childhood Care Programme in the area of the study.

Recommendations

1. Government should as a matter of fact sponsor teachers to read courses of Early Childhood Care Education at Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) and degree level to alleviate the problems of lack of qualified manpower to handle the effective implementation of early child care education programme.
2. The government should from time to time organize refresher courses and seminars on early childcare education delivery to teachers.
3. The proprietors should ensure allocating teachers that are experienced with good teaching method to man the affairs of ECCE in their centers.

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